

An Analysis of Social Entrepreneurship as a Route for Women Empowerment**Arvind Kumar Singh**

Research Scholar

Institute of Management, Commerce & Economics

Shri Ramswaroop Memorial University

Uttar Pradesh, INDIA

Dr. Jyoti Dewan

Associate Professor

Institute of Management, Commerce & Economics

Shri Ramswaroop Memorial University

Uttar Pradesh, INDIA

Abstract

Women empowerment movements have become one of the most compelling and focused actions taken unanimously across the globe. Empowerment is characterized as a procedure of change of power by which mistreated people increase some control over their lives and associated with the issues, which influences them straightforwardly. Women empowerment can be understood as a process to uplift and empower women to achieve all the desired and denied prospect of their lives. Social entrepreneurship is modern phenomena of business, to resolve pressing problems of society. This paper contains a systematic literature review to study and understand the various aspects and concept of women empowerment through existing scholarly literature. The paper also attempts to explore entrepreneurship structure and scope of social enterprises and their similarity and separation from traditional profit oriented business models. Attempt has been made to establish a link between Social entrepreneurial efforts for women empowerment and their efficacy. This study reveals the initiatives taken by social ventures to complement the empowerment movement for women and urge for greater initiative by government and corporate along-with different parts of society to spread social entrepreneurship business models at larger scale to expedite women empowerment.

Introduction

Empowerment and advancement of women and the movement towards achieving gender equivalence is that contemporary movement which is incessantly evolving and buzzing across the globe. Precisely we can say women empowerment refers to a process of empowering women with all the abnegated aspects of life.

In year 1995, The Fourth world conference of women held in China named as 'Beijing Declaration and Platform for Action' started a move to concentrate on women strengthening. The the United Nations Millennium Summit of Year 2000, furthered the movement initiated for the betterment for rightfulness of women in various fields such as education, health care and campaigns of gender equality declared as Goal no- 3 of Millennium Development Goals.

Women constitute approximately 50% of total population in the world and nearly 48% of the total population in India. Though after economic reforms taken in 1990, India emerged as one of the fastest growing economies in world and also could well become one of the largest economies but it is being crippled due to a lack of women's active participation in the workforce. Indian women who are self-dependent and enlightened with education will certainly contribute to the society by participating positively in the economic system and business world of the nation.

Our Indian guild is always regarded as patricentric where family structure is controlled and operated by men and women are treated as subordinate. They have to face a lot off social restrictions, imparity and negligence that tends to lose their self-confidence, which in turn creates employability barriers and because of that they are not able to become independent and in such a scenario, an entrepreneurship effort can be optimum source for empowering women as it helps them to attain their

goals. Entrepreneurship facilitates and incorporates in them the ability to take action and decisions by themselves.

This study is an attempt to collect the literature related to the initiative taken by social entrepreneurs for upliftment and empowerment of women and why women empowerment is need of this era. This paper seeks to explore some measures and working models which can be adopted by social enterprises for better results and analysis to understand impact of social enterprises on life of women and how we may encourage social entrepreneurship model for revitalization of women empowerment.

Limitation of the Study: Scope of this study is limited only to study and understand the concept of women empowerment & social entrepreneurship and their relationship with each other. The findings and conclusion drawn are based upon study of available secondary literature.

Key words explained:

Women Empowerment

As described in international conference of women (1990) "Women's empowerment is elucidated in five parts: women's feeling of self-esteem; their entitlement to have and to decide decisions; their entitlement to approach openings and assets; their entitlement to have the ability to control their own particular lives, both inside and outside the home; and their capacity to impact the bearing of social change to create a more just social and economic order, nationally and internationally."

Gender Equality

As per ILO (2007) Gender equality refers to "the enjoyment of equal rights, opportunities and treatment by men and women and by boys and girls in all spheres of life. It asserts that people's rights, responsibilities, social status and access to resources do not depend on whether they are born male or female. Gender equality grasps equality of chance and treatment, equality of compensation and access to sheltered and sound workplaces, equality in affiliation and aggregate dealing, equality in getting important vocation improvement, maternity assurance, a balance between work and home life."

Entrepreneurship

Konrad Billetz(2016)," Entrepreneurship is the potential to apprehend the larger picture, find wherein there may be any possibility to make someone's existence better, design hypotheses round those possibilities, and continually take a look at your assumptions. It is experimentation: a few experiments will work; many others will fail. It isn't always big deal, lavish lifestyle with handsome amount of net assets but it is all about putting religious and relentless efforts to pass on utilities to the world for making it ameliorate place once your time here has completed."

Social Entrepreneurs

According to Schwab Foundation- Social entrepreneur's drive social advancement and change in different fields including instruction, well-being, and condition and endeavor improvement. They seek after neediness easing objectives with entrepreneurial energy, business techniques and the bravery to improve and beat customary practices. A social business visionary, like a business visionary, forms solid and manageable associations, which are set up as not-for-benefits organizations. A social enterprise visionary is a pioneer or practical visionary who:

- Achieves expansive scale, fundamental and manageable social change through another development, an alternate approach, a more thorough utilization of known advances or methodologies, or a blend of these.
- Focuses above all else on the social as well as biological esteem creation and tries to streamline the monetary esteem creation.

- Innovates by finding another item, another administration, or another way to deal with a social issue.
- Continuously refines and adjusts approach in light of input.
- Combines the attributes practiced by Richard Branson and Mother Teresa. According to Ashoka Foundation Social entrepreneurs are the fundamental restorative power. They are framework changing entrepreneurs and from profound inside they, and subsequently their work, are focused on the benefit of all.

Social Enterprises/Social Entrepreneurship-

Shinu, A., Shastri, S.,(2015) Social enterprises are organizations with essentially social destinations whose surpluses are chiefly reinvested for that reason in the business or in the group, instead of being driven by the need to expand benefit for investors and proprietors'. They handle an extensive variety of social and natural issues and work in all parts of the economy, and utilize business answers for accomplishing open great. As per Centre for Social enterprise, 'A social enterprise is a business that utilizes entrepreneurial techniques to achieve social objectives and additionally nourishes benefits to a parent philanthropy or non-benefit to empower it to satisfy its very own greater amount social mission'.

Objective of Study

'Women' consisting half of the total human universe have been dealt a weaker part in family as well as in society. Thus our half the population is faced with a lot of problems, discrimination along with numerous kinds of obstacles in their lives. On the other hand Social entrepreneurship is a practice of innovative methods to solve most complex societal problems. This current research is an attempt to first to understand and explore the various concept and aspects related to empowerment of women, gaining deeper knowledge of Social entrepreneurship phenomena and then draw the conclusion based upon study of available literature, whether practice of Social entrepreneurship can be acknowledged as new ray of hope for women in their fight for empowerment or not.

Overview of Literature Review

For the purpose of literature review articles from scholar reviewed and academic peer reviewed journals papers, books, various reports, newspapers and websites with key words as entrepreneurship", "social entrepreneurship", "social entrepreneur", "social enterprise", "Social ventures", "Women empowerment", "models of women empowerment", "Methods & Initiative for women empowerment", Women empowerment Status, Social entrepreneurship and/for women empowerment" have been accessed.

Literature Review Composition

- Definition and Various Concept of Social and Commercial entrepreneurship related studies (Abroad) - 26%
- Social Entrepreneurship Studies in Indian context- 8%
- Woment empowerment concept,definiation, challenges and oppurtunity related studies(Abroad)- 16%
- Woment empowerment studies in Indian context- 14%
- Women empowerment determinant achievement through different modes of SE (Abroad)- 17%
- Women empowerment through different modes of SE in india- 19%

Historical Perspective of women empowerment and Social Entrepreneurship Studies-

A. Background of Empowerment and Women empowerment research and their determinant and Framework-

“Empowerment” term first used in year 1968 by Paulo Freire in his book named Pedagogy of the Oppressed. (Khanday, Shah, Mir, & Rasool, 2015) said that Empowerment can be understood as that concept having multifarious, multifaceted layer and multi-dimensional aspect. (Sharma, 1992) points out that term empowerment alludes to a scope of exercises from singular selfstatement to aggregate protection, dissent and preparation that test essential power relations. The status and part of women and related issues, have pulled in the consideration of the academicians, political scholars and social researchers both in creating and in addition created nations, halfway because of the recognition of the International Decade of women (1975-85) and mostly as a result of the broadly acknowledged truth that a general public based on the imbalance of men and women includes wastage of most precious asset human resource which no nation can manage.

We can say that there are a variety of understandings of the term empowerment due to its widespread usage. If empowerment is looked upon in terms of ability to make choices: to be disempowered therefore, implies to be denied choice. The notion of empowerment is that it is inescapably bound up with the condition of disempowerment and refers to the processes by which those who have been denied the ability to make choices acquire such ability. Different scholars has used various dimensions and terms to define empowerment however we have used Foley’s empowerment dimension to studied empowerment

Empowerment Dimensions

Dimensions	Definitions
Democratic	How much the populace progressively takes part in the way strategies are planned and tried
Economic	How many inhabitants control the wellspring of their pay, what alternatives they have, and how they are shielded from showcase changes.
Political	It alludes to the procedure by which a minority bunch increases more noteworthy capacity to impact results to support them. Basic esteems are social equity and an

	aware, reasonable treatment
Environmental	How bunches acquire the ability to control the space and nature in which they live.
Cultural	The advancement and fortification of social esteem as a wellspring of quality and solidarity.

Source: Extracted data from model given by Foley (1997).

“**Women Empowerment**” slogan was first uttered in the World Women Conference held in Mexico-City during June 9 to 2 July 1975. The first world conference on the status of women was met in Mexico City to harmonize with the 1975 as International Women's Year, seen to remind the global group that victimization of women kept on being a steady issue in a significant part of the world. According to the country report of the government of India (1995), —Empowerment implies moving from a place of upheld weakness to one of energy. It would advance women's characteristic quality and positive mental self-portrait.

Over the last two-three decade, women empowerment has been defined and explained in many ways by different organizations and various subject experts of gender and development depending on different contexts. Lauron, (2013) says that it is so complex to define women empowerment because of varied contexts of women, specifically of poor women. In the midst of many-sided quality of meaning of women empowerment, the vast majority of the writing concurred on specific ideas. Most specialists concur that women empowerment is a procedure of progress, empowering individuals to pick up the ability to be key players themselves. **The element of “agency” is common in most definitions of empowerment.** (Batliwala &Srilatha,1993) said that Women's empowerment could be portrayed as a procedure in which women increase more noteworthy offer of control over assets material, human and scholarly like knowledge, data information, thoughts, and budgetary assets like cash and access to cash and control over basic leadership in the home, group, society and country, and to pick up control. The phrase women's empowerment has used to relate with women's battle for social equity and justice. Kabeer, 2001, defines Women empowerment as the development in women's capacity to settle on vital life decisions in a setting where this capacity was beforehand denied to them and Women's capacity to settle on key life decisions and make strategic choices is an activity of their 'Agency'.

Chakrabarti,S.,& Biswas, C. S. (2012) says that women ought to be enabled at the same time with men and given flexibility of decision. Gender equality and empowerment of women assume a basic part being developed through a multiplier procedure; an engaged lady not just enables her family, she engages the general public too. Distinguishing women's empowerment as a worldwide issue, the Government of India (2002) has additionally seen empowerment as a dynamic, multidimensional process, which empowers women to discover their personality and understand their maximum capacity in all circles of life. Be that as it may, the accomplishment of a specific standard relies on the collaboration between the social, political and financial parts of women's life.

According to report of World Bank, Women perform approximately 66 percent of the total world’s work, bring forth 50% of the foodstuffs but able to gain only 10% of the total income and enjoy ownership rights of 1% of total property. (Women Business and Law, World Bank, 2011). As per (National Women Development Policy, 2008), because of incongruities amongst men and women prevail as far as education, physical wellbeing, business and employment openings, control over resources, individual security and interest in the political procedure that made women impaired, which restrains the nation's capacity to accomplish its maximum capacity. Duflo, E. (2012) explained that Women empowerment and economic advancement are firmly related: in one course, improvement alone can assume a noteworthy part in driving down imbalance amongst men and women; in the other heading, engaging women may lead development.

Precisely we may say that Empowerment of women would mean equipping women to be economically independent, self-reliant, have a positive self-esteem to enable them to face any difficult situation and they should be able to participate in developmental activities. The empowered women should be able

to participate in the process of decision-making. Education will be the one of key factor which would play the most crucial role in empowering women.

Women Empowerment Framework

This structure was produced by Sara Hlupekile, a gender orientation master from Lusaka Zambia (1990)

LEVELS OF EMPOWERMENT	DESCRIPTION
CONTROL 	Women and men have equal control over factors of production and distribution of benefits, without dominance or subordination.
PARTICIPATION 	Women have equal participation in decision-making in all programs and policies.
CONSCIENTIZATION 	Women believe that gender roles can be changed and gender equality is possible.
ACCESS 	Women gain access to resources such as land, labor, credit, training, marketing facilities, public services, and benefits on an equal basis with men. Reforms of law and practice may be prerequisites for such access.
WELFARE 	Women's material needs, such as food, income, and medical care, are met.

The model is expressly political, connecting women's inequality and destitution to auxiliary abuse. Accordingly, with a specific end goal to secure women's equality and empowerment, both really and monetarily, women must be engaged. The apparatus looks at a program, for example, a wellbeing or training intercession, to survey how it impacts the five levels of empowerment, i.e., adversely, decidedly, or impartially. It hypothesizes a climbing level of equality impacts that can be followed and surveyed after some time to check whether movement or relapse is occurring.

Determinants and dimensions to measure women's empowerment

Mahmud, S., Shah, N. M., & Becker, S. (2012) have done their studies on the rural women of Bangladesh to measure empowerment status and conceptualize empowerment as a dynamic, multi-dimensional process that is strongly influenced by resources and settings, measured by the four determinants: age (demographic status); household wealth (economic status); women's schooling (social status); and media exposure to TV or radio. These result in four dimensions of empowerment: self-esteem; control of resources; decision-making; and mobility (although not simultaneously). The researcher find that empowerment processes are not directly observable, but that indicators or proxies can be used, which need to be relevant to the particular context. On the basis of their studies they have developed a model consists of determinants and dimensions required to measure the empowerment status of women in rural Bangladesh.

B. Background of Social entrepreneurship research and Models

The term 'entrepreneur' was started in French financial aspects in the seventeenth and eighteenth hundreds of years, to signify 'somebody who embraces' a venture or any action. The association of hazard with entrepreneurship was produced just in the seventeenth century by the business analyst Richard Cantillon saw entrepreneur as a 'daring person'. In any case, the term 'entrepreneur' got its specific significance from Jean Baptiste say in the nineteenth century, when he expressed that the entrepreneur is one who shifts financial assets from a zone of lower to a region of higher efficiency and more prominent yields. He didn't accentuation the significance of progress and advancement inside a monetary framework; rather, he depicted the entrepreneur as a specialist. According to Thompson (2002) Entrepreneurs are people, who often create and innovate to build something of recognized value around perceived opportunities. They can be found in all walks of life and create social, artistic or financial value. Kao (1993) defines entrepreneurship as the way toward including something new utilizing innovativeness and something else and imaginative to create riches for the individual and enhancing society.

It isn't precisely known when the term 'social entrepreneurship' was utilized to start with, however it was likely in a scholarly distribution by William N. Parker in 1954. He announced in an article published by The Journal of Economic History about: "To the individual German in the mining business, each of the three kinds of action showed up as outlets for big business and desire. The first is most clearly "financial entrepreneurship" on a vocation, and contributed unmistakably to the working of the economy and, under other ideal conditions, to its development. The person's enthusiasm for the second (which might be called "social entrepreneurship") relied upon the ease of the German social structure, the measures for progression, and the person's own fretfulness." according to Parker(1954) social entrepreneurship added to an expanded social portability that enabled individuals from the regular workers to accomplish generally generously compensated, intrapreneurial initiative positions by showing entrepreneurial conduct. The expression "social entrepreneurship" has increased more prominent fame and visibility since the late 1990. As indicated by Nicholls (2006), prevalence of social entrepreneurship is developing extensively with expanded consideration in broad communications, scholarly fields, government, foundations and partnerships with an end goal to better comprehend the idea.

Santos, Filipe M (2012) differentiates social entrepreneurship among different sorts of business association; doubtlessly modern economies incorporate distinctive kinds of business associations with various administration models: freely possessed companies, family-claimed organizations, associations, and cooperatives. However, and regardless of their disparities (proprietorship structure, benefit versus non-benefit), all these authoritative structures share a shared trait – they race to safeguard the interests of the overwhelming hierarchical coalition, be they investors, proprietor chiefs, accomplices or individuals. Social entrepreneurship activities, interestingly, don't appear to keep running for the self-enthusiasm of its prevailing coalition be that as it may, rather, give off an

impression of keeping running for the advantage of particular clients or society in general. However, social business people communicate in the market for assets and administrations with different sorts of monetary performers. It is essential to comprehend what their part is and how they work. According to Dees, J. G. (1998), Research writing separates customary entrepreneurship from social entrepreneurship on the grounds of primarily what persuades these business visionaries – with conventional business visionaries prodded on by cash and social business people driven by mission-related effect. Business person's measure esteem made through the riches gathered, while social business people measure an incentive through the effect on the social mission.

(Martin and Osberg, 2007) contends the word entrepreneurship is a blended gift. On the positive side, it implies an uncommon, natural capacity to detect and follow up on circumstance, joining out-of-the-container thinking with a remarkable brand of assurance to make or achieve something new to the world. On the negative side, entrepreneurship is an ex post-term, on the grounds that entrepreneurial exercises require a section of time before their actual effect is obvious, they think about social entrepreneurship as entrepreneurial action with an installed social reason. As per (Haugh, 2007) Social entrepreneurship has likewise been known as the synchronous quest for financial, social, and ecological objectives by venturesome endeavors. According to (Noruzi, Westover, and Rahimi, 2010) Social entrepreneurship is characterized as the act of reacting to showcase disappointments with transformative and fiscally feasible advancements went for taking care of social issues. These three basic parts:

- 1. Response to Market disappointments **
- 2. Transformative advancement**
- 3. Monetary Sustainability**

The essential idea of social endeavors has two components:

i. A social target

ii. A long haul arrangement situated towards social needs.

To help the primary component Campbell, S.(1998) said 'social mission as a fundamental objective of the wander, superseding the quest for benefit boost'. The second component concentrates on looking for an answer for the social issue tended to. Bugg-Levine, A., Kogut, B., and Kulatilaka, N. (2012) stick point that these plans of action are equipped towards a perpetual answer for a social issue, making another adjust that ensures persisting advantages. Dees, J. G. (2012) weights on When looked by the difficulty between "critical thinking" considering and the way of life of philanthropy or altruism, the social business visionary picks the first.

We may conclude it as Entrepreneurs are people, who often create and innovate to build something of recognized value around perceived opportunities and entrepreneurship defined as the process of adding something new using creativity and something different and innovative for the purpose of creating wealth for the individual and adding value to society. Social entrepreneurs are individuals with innovative solutions to society's most pressing social problems. They are yearning and diligent, handling real social issues and offering new thoughts for a wide-scale change. As opposed to leaving societal necessities to the legislature or business segments, social entrepreneurs find what isn't working and tackle the issue by changing the framework, spreading the arrangement, and inducing whole social orders to take new jumps."

Typology and scope of Social Enterprise

Yunus, Lehman and Ortega (2010) referred to that 'in the entrepreneur framework, there are two outrageous sorts of corporate bodies that can be recognized. From one viewpoint, organizations can be viewed as benefit augmenting organizations, whose object is to make investor esteem. On the other, non-benefit associations exist to satisfy social destinations'. Social business endeavors to obtain from and combine these two contradicting ideas. The figure underneath demonstrates a graph that outlines social business/endeavor.

Social Business versus Benefit Maximizing Business and Not revenue driven Organizations (show given by Yunus, Lehman and Ortega (2010))

Yunus, Lehman and Ortega (2010) describes, “its primary purpose is to serve society, a social business has products, services, customers, markets, expenses and revenues like a ‘regular’ enterprise. It is a no--loss, no--dividend, self--sustaining company that repays its owners’ investments.” On the basis of above study Lauron, (2013) explained in a social business, the cost has to be covered by the earnings of the business but investors do not earn profit. Investors may claim the initial capital without interest after it is rolled over. Unlike the profit maximizing business, investors in social business have to be cause-oriented rather than profit oriented. As an organization, social business has to be managed like a ‘regular’ business and dislike philanthropy, despite the fact that the goal is unique in relation to a benefit augmenting organization. While it endeavors to accomplish the social target, social organizations need to recuperate their full costs so it can act naturally maintaining. The entrepreneur never expects to make benefits for themselves as there are no profits. Surplus or benefit must be utilized either to grow the business to profit more individuals who don't approach these items and administrations.

Lauron, (2013) as per her observation in Philippines has also given a typology or scope of social enterprises. It is usually in a form of fair trade organization, microfinance institution, cooperative, and community--based enterprise serving the fishers, farmers, and the indigenous people, social business and small and medium non--- profit organizations that have embraced a social mission as the core of the business.

Typology/scope given by Lauron, J. F. A. (2013)

Impact of SE for Women Empowerment in Indian Context -

British Council of United Kingdom has conducted a detailed study to assess the impact of social entrepreneurial effort on women empowerment in India. They have conducted a four stage research

process during year 2016 to March-2017. Primary data gathered through in-depth interview of 27 number of key Indian Social entrepreneurs and detailed structured questionnaire consisting qualitative and quantitative question also get filled by 228 number of SE beneficiaries and out of them 161 responses used for final processing. Following are the major highlight of that research-

‘How does your social enterprises help empower women and girls?’

Sl No	Aspect of Empowerment	Impact of SEs
1	Providing Education	60%
2	Counseling/Support advice	35%
3	Providing Healthcare	8%
4	Development Skills	75%
5	Creating Jobs	45%
6	Campaigning	10%
7	Giving women voice in their society	40%
8	Affordable Childcare	5%
9	Tackling human trafficking	2%
10	Tackling violence	10%
11	Other Ways	40%

Research Gap/Unaddressed issue-

Women empowerment has become one of most burning and pressing social issue globally. Lot of efforts has made to achieve women empowerment and also many researches had been done to study it. Social entrepreneurship is contemporary phenomena to resolve critical social issues which are also contributing to achieve women empowerment. Since this is a new field of knowledge and fascinate many researchers for study. However after extensive literature review, following study gap has been observed which seeks our attention to do research and are delianated below given issues-

- It has observed that in Indian context especially in central north India very few studies have been conducted to measure the women empowerment status and also out of them a lot of studies analyzed and conclude with use of secondary data only.
- In earlier researches maximum focus have been given to measure only one or two variable of empowerment like economic empowerment and educational empowerment only and other major variable like equality in work place, decision making power in personal and professional field, Job satisfaction and willingness to working, training and development (intellectual growth) issues have not been touched in depth.
- It has also examined, since in India very few researches have been conducted to establish any linkage between women empowerment and SE so there is wide scope to study and measure the impact of Social entrepreneurial efforts invested to achieve the goals of women empowerment.

Conclusion-

After an extensive literature review, personal observation and discussions the following key points have been identified

- Women empowerment has been recognized as a global issue of concern and nowadays zealous efforts are being pressed into service to promote it.
- Social Entrepreneurship is gradually empering as an effective contemporary solution for women empowerment.
- In developing economies like India, there is immense potential for growth of Social enterprise business model. Government and other agencies should pay enough attention and focus for development of more SE ventures.

Bibliography

1. *Women empowerment definition(1990), ' Guidelines on Women's Empowerment' Available Online at: <http://www.un.org/popin/unfpa/taskforce/guide/iatfwemp.gdl.html>*

2. International Labour Organization.(2007).ABC of women workers' rights and gender equality. *Journal of Chemical Information and Modeling*, (Second, pp. 1–211). Geneva 22,: International Labour Office. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9781107415324.004>
3. CEO of Frameri Konrad Billetz(2016), 'Entrepreneurship Defined: What It Means to Be an Entrepreneur' Available Online at:<http://www.businessnewsdaily.com/7275-entrepreneurshipdefined.html>
4. Schwab Foundation, 'What is a social entrepreneur?' Available Online at: <http://www.schwabfound.org/content/what-social-entrepreneur>
5. Ashoka Foundation, ' Social Entrepreneurship: Building the Field' Available Online at: <https://www.ashoka.org/en/focus/social-entrepreneurship>
6. Shinu, A., Shastri, S.,(2015), ' A Comparative Study Of Business Models Of Social And Commercial Entrepreneurial Ventures With Special Reference To Social And Financial Impact Assessment' Available Online at: <http://hdl.handle.net/10603/44825>
7. Centre for Social enterprise, 'What is social enterprise' Available Online at: <https://centreforsocialenterprise.com/what-is-social-enterprise/>
8. Freire, P. (1968). *Pedagogy of the oppressed*. New York: Seabury Press.(Book) 9. Sharma Kumud, —Grassroots Organisations and Women's Empowerment: Some Issues in the Contemporary Debate, in Samya Shakti, Centre for Women's Development Studies, New Delhi, Vol. VI, 1991-92,p. 29.
10. Khanday, M. I., Shah, B. A., Mir, P. A., & Rasool, P. (2015). Empowerment of Women in India: Historical Perspective. *European Academic Research*, 2(11), 14494–14505.
11. Lauron, J. F. A. (2013). *Empowering Women in the Philippines through Social Enterprises*, Unpublished doctoral dissertation). *Social Development: History and Perspectives* College of Social Work and Community Development University of the Philippines-Diliman 0–41.(Dissertation)
12. Noruzi, M. R., Westover, J. H., & Rahimi, G. R. (2010). An Exploration of Social Entrepreneurship in the Entrepreneurship Era. *Asian Social Science*, 6(6), 3–10. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICAMS.2010.5553306>
13. UNWOMEN. (1975). *World Conference of the International Women's Year . Mexico City (19 June to 2 July 1975). First World Conference, (July 1975).* <https://doi.org/E.76.5V.1> (Conference proceeding)
14. Khanday, M. I., Shah, B. A., Mir, P. A., & Rasool, P. (2015). Empowerment of Women in India: Historical Perspective. *European Academic Research*, 2(11), 14494–14505. (Journal)
15. Batliwala, S., *Asian-South Pacific Bureau of Adult Education, Freedom from Hunger Campaign, & Action for Development (Eds.). (1993). Empowerment of women in South Asia: Concepts and practices.* New Delhi, India: FFHC/AD Program Officer.
16. India. Department of Women and Child Development. (1996). *Fourth World Conference on Women, Beijing 1995: Country report.* New Delhi?: Government of India, Department of Women and Child Development, Ministry of Human Resource Development.
17. Kabeer, N. (2001). Conflicts Over Credit: Re-Evaluating the Empowerment Potential of Loans to Women in Rural Bangladesh. *World Development*, 29(1), 63-84. doi:10.1016/s0305- 750x(00)00081-4
18. Chakrabarti, S., & Biswas, C. S. (2012). An Exploratory analysis of women's empowerment in India: A Structural Equation Modeling Approach. *Journal of Development Studies*, 48(1), 164– 180. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00220388.2011.615920>
19. Government of India (2002) *Committee on empowerment of women (2001–2002).* August, 2001 Laid in Rajya Sabha, New Delhi on 24. (2002), 1923, 1–34.
20. Duflo, E. (2012), *Women Empowerment and Economic Development*, *Journal of Economic Literature*, American Economic Association Stable 50(4), 1051–1079. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/23644911>
21. *Role_of_National_Women_Development_Policy.* (n.d.).Children Affairs. (2011). *National Women Development Policy 2011*,Ministry of Women and Children Affairs, Bangladesh <https://www.unescogym.org/wp-content/uploads/2017/05/Bangladesh-National-Women-Policy-2011English.pdf>(Government

22. Huis, M. A., Hansen, N., Otten, S., & Lensink, R. (2017). *A three-dimensional model of women's empowerment: Implications in the field of microfinance and future directions*. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 8(SEP). <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2017.01678>
23. Thompson, J. L. (2002). *The world of the social entrepreneur*. *International Journal of Public Sector Management*, 15(5), 412-431. doi:10.1108/09513550210435746
24. Kao, R. W., Kao, R. R., & Kao, K. R. (1993). *Evolution of Entrepreneurship: Toward Stewardship-based Economics*. *World Encyclopedia of Entrepreneurship*. doi:10.4337/9781849808453.00023
25. Parker, W.N. (1954), "Entrepreneurial Opportunities and Response in the German Economy," in *Explorations in Entrepreneurial History*, vol. 7, no.1, pp. 26–36.
26. Nicholls, A. (2006). *Social Entrepreneurship: New Models of Sustainable Social Change*, Oxford University Press (p. 444). Oxford. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9781107415324.004>
27. Martin, R. L., & Osberg, S. (2007). *Social Entrepreneurship: The Case for Definition*. *Stanford Social Innovation Review*, 29–39. Retrieved from <http://www.ngobiz.org/picture/File/Social-Entrepreneur-The-Case-of-Definition.pdf>
28. Santos, F. M. (2012). *A Positive Theory of Social Entrepreneurship*. *Source Journal of Business Ethics*, 111(3), 335–351. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-012-1413-4>
29. Dees, J. G. (1998). *Enterprising nonprofits*. *Harvard Business Review*, 76(1), 54–67. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemgeo.2004.12.024>
30. Haugh, H. 2007. *New Strategies for a Sustainable Society: The Growing Contribution of Social Entrepreneurship*. *Business Ethics Quarterly*, 17(4): 743-749.
31. Noruzi, M. R., Westover, J. H., & Rahimi, G. R. (2010). *An Exploration of Social Entrepreneurship in the Entrepreneurship Era*. *Asian Social Science*, 6(6), 3–10. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICAMS.2010.5553306>
32. Campbell, S. (1998). *Social entrepreneurship: how to develop new social-purpose business ventures*. *Health Care Strategic Management*, 16(5), 17–18. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.1597706>
33. Bugg-Levine, A., Kogut, B., & Kulatilaka, N. (2012, January). *A new approach to funding social enterprises*. *Harvard Business Review*. 90(1-2), 3-7.
34. Dees, J. G. (2012). *A Tale of Two Cultures: Charity, Problem Solving, and the Future of Social Entrepreneurship*. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 111(3), 321-334. doi:10.1007/s10551-012-1412-5
35. Foley, J. (1997). *The dimensions of empowerment*. 29th Annual International Conference of the Community Development Society, University of New Orleans.
36. Longwe, S. H. (1991). *Gender awareness: the missing element in the Third World development project*. In T. Wallace & C. Marchm (Eds.), *Changing perceptions: writings on gender and development* (pp. 149–57). Oxfam. Retrieved from <https://www.popline.org/node/335992>
37. Alexandra Pittman(2011)," *Women's Empowerment Framework*"available online at: <http://awidme.pbworks.com/w/page/36322701/Women%27s%20Empowerment%20Framework>
38. Mahmud, S., Shah, N. M., & Becker, S. (2012). *Measurement of Women's Empowerment in Rural Bangladesh*. *World Development*, 40(3), 610–619. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.worlddev.2011.08.003>
39. Alter K (2007) *Social enterprise typology*, Virtue Ventures LLC, available at: www.virtueventures.com/files/setypology.pdf
40. British Council (2017), *The role of social enterprise in supporting women's empowerment in India* online available on https://www.britishcouncil.org/sites/default/files/british_council_social_enterprise_womens_empowerment_in_india_web_final.pdf